

GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE AND GREEN ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonning yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tish yo‘lida ko‘rayotgan chora-tadbirlari, xalqaro majburiyatlari va ekologik barqarorlikni ta‘minlash bo‘yicha strategik yondashuvlari tahlil qilinadi. Energetika va qishloq xo‘jaligi sohalarining iqlim o‘zgarishiga ta‘siri, issiqxona gazlari chiqindilarini kamaytirish bo‘yicha Parij kelishuvi doirasidagi maqsadlar, COP29 anjumani doirasidagi tashabbuslar va ekologik ta‘lim, yashil texnologiyalar, hamda yoshlarning roli alohida e‘tiborga olingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, O‘zbekiston, iqlim o‘zgarishi, COP29, Parij kelishuvi, energiya samaradorligi, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya, ekologik barqarorlik, cho‘llanish, Orolbo‘yi, yashil moliyalashtirish, bioxilma-xillik, ekologik ta‘lim.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются меры, предпринимаемые Узбекистаном на пути перехода к «зелёной экономике», его международные обязательства и стратегические подходы к обеспечению экологической устойчивости. Особое внимание уделено влиянию энергетического и сельскохозяйственного секторов на изменение климата, целям по сокращению выбросов парниковых газов в рамках Парижского соглашения, инициативам в рамках конференции COP29, а также роли экологического образования, зелёных технологий и участия молодежи.

Ключевые слова: зелёная экономика, Узбекистан, изменение климата, COP29, Парижское соглашение, энергоэффективность, возобновляемая энергия, экологическая устойчивость, опустынивание, Приаралье, зелёное финансирование, биоразнообразие, экологическое образование.

Annotation. This article analyzes Uzbekistan's measures in transitioning to a green economy, its international commitments, and strategic approaches to ensuring environmental sustainability. Particular attention is given to the impact of the energy

and agricultural sectors on climate change, the goals under the Paris Agreement to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, initiatives within the COP29 framework, as well as the role of environmental education, green technologies, and youth engagement.

Keywords: green economy, Uzbekistan, climate change, COP29, Paris Agreement, energy efficiency, renewable energy, environmental sustainability, desertification, Aral Sea region, green financing, biodiversity, environmental education.

Economic and environmental crises often originate from the same sources and influence each other. This is because the current economic model strives for short-term profits without considering ecosystems or the environmental and social consequences. In the context of globalization, the failures of the market economy in addressing existing economic issues have given rise to a new trend — the "green economy." This emerging economic paradigm seeks strategies to resolve crises that have hindered global development in recent years. For instance, the consequences of climate change, food shortages, economic and financial crises triggered by the pandemic, and slow progress in poverty reduction have been key factors in the UN Environment Programme (UNEP) in shaping the concept of a "green economy."

Today, not only Central Asian countries but the entire global community is striving to find solutions to the challenges and threats posed by climate change. These include the increase in greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere, rising surface temperatures, water scarcity, frequent natural disasters, desertification, and more. Experts warn that climate change can not only cause new types of natural disasters but also multiply the destructive power of existing ones, potentially reaching uncontrollable levels.

International organizations and scientific communities predict that climate change will lead to various socio-economic issues in different regions of the world. According to the World Bank, climate change may trigger large-scale internal migration, and by 2050, about 216 million people from six regions of the world may be forced to relocate. Among these regions is Central Asia, including over 5 million people — a clear

indication of the urgency of this issue for regional states. In response, the Republic of Uzbekistan has issued a number of Presidential decrees and resolutions aimed at mitigating the negative consequences of climate change and addressing existing challenges. For instance, due to the annual increase in average regional temperatures, leading to water shortages, soil salinization, and land degradation, Uzbekistan adopted Presidential Resolution No. 233 on June 24, 2024, “On Measures to Create a Climate-Resilient Agro-Ecosystem and Increase the Adaptability of Agricultural Producers to Climate Risks.” The resolution also approved a National Program aimed at adapting agriculture to climate change and mitigating the sector’s negative impact on the environment.

Key priorities for the implementation of the National Program include:

- Efficient organization of climate change-related activities in affected regions;
- Implementation of international grant projects in agriculture under climate change conditions;
- Effective use of natural resources in climate-vulnerable areas and improvement of agricultural technologies;
- Development of climate-adaptive agricultural measures;
- Sustainable use and protection of pastures.

The resolution also outlines collaboration with the UN Green Climate Fund to support and encourage farmers through the program “Expanding Climate-Resilient Agricultural Practices in Uzbekistan and Mitigating the Sector's Impact,” with an allocated budget of USD 200 million. In addition, grants from international organizations such as the European Union, the Global Environment Facility (GEF), the German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ), and the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) will support climate-related projects in the Aral Sea region and across Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan’s energy sector accounts for 89% of emissions, and agriculture contributes 13%. The country’s energy intensity per unit of GDP is among the highest globally. Under the Paris Agreement, Uzbekistan has pledged to reduce

greenhouse gas emissions by 35% relative to GDP by 2030. Experts emphasize the importance of sustainable approaches in energy, water management, and agriculture to address climate change, along with enhancing resilience to natural disasters, incorporating green principles into public budgeting, assessing climate risks in public investment projects, mobilizing green international finance and trade, creating green jobs, supporting private sector involvement, and developing a climate-conscious workforce.

At the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP29) to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change held in Baku in November 2024, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan delivered a speech at the World Leaders' Summit. He emphasized that climate change has become one of the most critical global threats, directly influencing geopolitical tensions. Issues such as poverty reduction, food and energy security, and access to drinking water and resources are becoming increasingly urgent. Uzbekistan plans to raise the share of "green" energy to 40%, and projects on electric vehicles, green hydrogen clusters, and solar and wind generation hubs are underway.

Within COP29, high-level events are scheduled to address land degradation, combat desertification, promote environmental education, and highlight the role of youth in advancing the climate agenda. Over 20 additional events are planned at Uzbekistan's national pavilion, focusing on resolving the socio-environmental challenges of the Aral Sea region, developing the green economy, introducing renewable energy and water-saving technologies, ensuring food security, preserving biodiversity, and more.

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